

Discovery of multiple instances of extremely redshifted Einstein Cross with system of six images of background galaxy around the lensing galaxy.

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Abstract

Multiple instances of 6 image system Einstein Cross have been observed in the first deep image of the James Webb Space Telescope. The image was released on 12-07-2022. (updated 02-08-2022: Discussion about famous galaxy Glass-Z13 has been added at the end)

Article

I. Cases of Einstein Cross with not previously observed six image systems of lensed galaxies

This article documents the discovery of multiple instances of Einstein Cross with not previously observed systems of 6 images of the background galaxies. All these images have been found through a manual survey of the deep image that was released by the JWST team dated 12-07-2022. Images of background galaxies appear to be extremely redshifted and are symmetrically lurking from behind such galaxies which are already located at huge distances from Earth. Existence of such systems raises some serious questions regarding the mechanism by which symmetrical six images are formed around the lensing galaxies and also what invisible stuff exists behind far off galaxies which shows up only when magnified through the gravitational lensing of the intervening galaxies. Author may have opinion about the extent of their distances however only a reference to a previous publication¹ is sufficient here. Following is the JWST main deep field image:

NASA, ESA, CSA, and STScI -

There are multiple instances of 6 images Einstein Cross systems available in this image. This article is going to present many of them but not all. Following are such instances:

Sr No	Location Within the Main Image	Zoom of the Einstein Cross
1		

2

Lower left corner of the main image

3

Middle of Bottom of the main image

4

Bottom, just right of the middle of the main image

5

Bottom Right Corner of the main image

6

Bottom Right Corner of the main image

7

Bottom Right of the main image

Right side near middle of the main image

9

Almost middle of the main image

10

Near middle of the main image

Near middle of the main image

12

Near middle of the main image

Upper left corner of the main image

14

Upper near middle of the main image

15

Upper near middle of the main image

Upper right corner of the main image

Almost middle of the main image

Middle of the main image

Middle of the main image

Right side near middle of the main image

Bottom right of the main image

22

Middle of bottom of the main image

Middle of right of the main image

Left of the middle of the main image

Top of left side of the main image

II. Update (02-08-2022)

Glass-z13 was presented in July-2022 as a candidate for the most distant galaxy ever observed. Following is the image of Glass-z13:

NASA/STScI/GLASS-JWST program: R. Naidu, G. Brammer, T. Treu. - Image source: <https://earthsky.org/space/oldest-galaxy-yet-seen-by-webb-telescope/> (image source) Credits source: <https://www.syfy.com/syfy-wire/bad-astronomy-glass-z13-may-be-most-distant-g>

The point of this update is that the image of Glass-z13 is filled with innumerable small red dots and in fact more than 6 red dots are visible around the galaxy Glass-z13 which seems due to the greater zoom level of this image. In my opinion, all these smaller red dots are extremely redshifted galaxies. The smaller red dots are clearly visible throughout the background of this image. Glass-z13 has not acted as a lensing galaxy in this image. That means more than 6 red dots discussed above as visible around Glass-z13 do not make up a case of Einstein Cross. However, for all the instances of the Einstein Cross as presented in section I, the lensed galaxies that are repeated six times in every case might have come from the population of smaller red dot galaxies which are visible throughout the background of the image of Glass-z13 galaxy. Again, this article/ report is not commenting on the distance scale of the background galaxies as the method to estimate these distances has been explained in the reference given in the endnotes section.

ⁱ Rafique, Khuram. (2019). Distance Anomalies - Book: "Philosophy Unscrambles Dark Matter". In Philosophy Unscrambles Dark Matter. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3817879>